

Practice Abstract no. 35

Consumers & citizens' views on gains linked to personal data sharing

The #Data4Food Cluster comprising the [DRG4Food](#), [FOODITY](#), [FoodDataQuest](#), and [SOSFood](#) projects organised a joint workshop in June 2025 to discuss challenges, enablers, and gains related to data sharing and AI-driven solutions for sustainable food systems. Two breakout room sessions explored perspectives from both consumers/citizens and industry/food system actors on data sharing and AI in food systems.

This practice abstract discusses consumers/ citizens' views on the gains regarding personal data sharing, particularly any potential societal and ecosystem benefits that outweigh concerns and risks associated with the sharing of personal data.

- **Personalisation and user experience**, including the possibility of customising the services used, and the data shared, improving the overall experience; having a more personalised experience with only useful information aligned with our data; access to personalised recommendations for healthy and sustainable consumption, as well as personalised health and nutrition advice.
- **Societal value and sustainability**, referring to opportunities to generate increased societal value beyond commercial interests; including promoting healthy diets, fostering the sustainability of European (and world) food systems; generating more awareness among citizens and encouraging more sustainable consumption habits; and driving a positive impact on climate change mitigation and nature conservation.
- **Innovation opportunities by leveraging data**, in which the rules for using (personal) data could be more flexible with a clear and transparent use of data to increase innovation in strategic EU areas and making available tools and services that are free to use.

The aforementioned information is available and further detailed in the joint report developed by the #Data4Food Cluster "What Helps and What Hurts When Sharing Data for Sustainable Food Solutions."

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